

TOURIST INFRASTRUCTURE AND MOUNTAIN RELIEF USE: A COMPARISON OF THE CARPATHIANS AND THE TATRAS

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Abstract

The Carpathian Mountains, Europe's second-longest mountain range, extend approximately 1,500 kilometers across Central and Eastern Europe and are a significant region for tourism. Around 80% of the range lies within the borders of Romania, Slovakia, and Poland, making these three countries key stakeholders in the region's tourism development. While the morphology and scenery of the mountains share many similarities, the approaches taken by each country to promote and develop tourism differ significantly. Romania emphasizes scenic routes and extensive hiking opportunities, Slovakia focuses on ski resorts and year-round outdoor activities, while Poland capitalizes on well-developed mountain tourism hubs like Zakopane. This study examines the tourism infrastructure in the Carpathian regions of Romania, Slovakia, and Poland, focusing on key aspects such as accommodations, facilities for winter and summer activities, and transportation networks. By comparing these three countries, the analysis aims to evaluate their offerings for tourists, including lodging, ski slopes or hiking trails. This comparison provides insights into how each nation leverages its portion of the Carpathians to support and grow its tourism sector.

Keywords: *Carpathian Mountains, tourism infrastructure, Romania, Slovakia, Poland, ski resorts, accommodation, mountain tourism.*

INTRODUCTION

The Carpathian Mountains, stretching approximately 1,700 kilometers across Central and Eastern Europe, represent a region of significant tourist interest. The Carpathians are an important source of natural wealth, serving as a stronghold for large carnivores, hosting over half of the continent's populations of bears, wolves, and lynxes, as well as a third of European plant species, including 481 endemic species (Kichkovskyy, 2010). Romania, Slovakia, and Poland, which together host about 80% of this mountain range, have adopted different strategies to capitalize on the region's tourism potential. Although the morphology and landscapes are similar, each country focuses on different aspects: Romania emphasizes mountain trails and scenic roads, Slovakia develops ski resorts and recreational activities, while Poland promotes famous resorts, such as Zakopane. The Carpathians in these three countries share common geomorphological features, with steep peaks, forested slopes, and glacial valleys. In Romania, the Carpathians are divided into the Southern, Eastern, and Western Carpathians; in Poland, they are located in the south (the Tatra Mountains); and in Slovakia, they are in the north, with the High Tatras (Vysoké Tatry) and Low Tatras (Nízke Tatry).

Tourism in this area focuses on similar activities, with weather conditions playing an important role in shaping preferences for summer vacations (hiking) and winter vacations

(skiing), as well as relaxation or treatment activities (spa resorts) (Wieckowski, 2020). Notably, ski tourism has developed into a significant segment of the winter tourism industry, attracting approximately 350 million annual ski visits worldwide (Steiger et al. 2019). Currently, there is also a shift from traditional tourism centered on hiking and spa resorts to a product more oriented toward fun and entertainment in these destinations (Gajdosikova et al. 2019).

Recent studies have analyzed mountain tourism in Central and Eastern Europe, in Slovakia, Poland, and Romania, highlighting various aspects such as skiing tourism, hiking, cultural tourism, and the impact of climate change on these activities. Research on skiing tourism emphasizes the economic and infrastructural importance of winter sports in these regions. Poland and Slovakia are recognized as key destinations due to their developed ski resorts and Romania's Carpathian slopes offer emerging potential in the sector (Gajdosikova et al. 2019, Herman et al. 2021, Krzesiwo et al. 2019). Beyond winter tourism, studies on hiking and cultural tourism underscore the significance of the Carpathians and Tatras as year-round attractions, where visitors engage in ecotourism, heritage exploration, and outdoor recreation, reflecting the diverse tourism portfolio of these mountain areas (Banhidi et al. 2014, Mokras-Grabowska, 2017). Besides these, the impact of climate change on mountain tourism has been widely examined, with findings suggesting a reduction in snow reliability and an increasing shift towards alternative tourism activities, such as nature-based and cultural tourism, to mitigate the negative effects of warming trends (Demiroglu et al. 2015, Dinčă et al. 2014, Jodłowski et al. 2023). These studies collectively illustrate the evolving dynamics of mountain tourism in Slovakia, Poland, and Romania, providing a comprehensive understanding of its economic, cultural, and environmental dimensions.

This study compares the tourism infrastructure in the Carpathians to highlight both the strengths and challenges of each country, providing insight into how these countries leverage their mountain natural resources to support tourism development. In the Carpathian region, tourism activities occur year-round, but seasonality significantly influences tourist flows, with peaks during the summer and winter seasons (Faracik et al. 2009). In summer, mountain trails attract hiking enthusiasts, while in winter, ski slopes become the main destinations. These seasonal dynamics are essential for understanding tourist behavior. The analysis focused on three main indicators: the network of mountain trails, the number of ski slopes, and accommodation units, which are crucial for defining the region's tourism potential. The trails and slopes reflect the main seasonal activities, while the number of accommodation units indicates the region's capacity to support tourist flows. These indicators are fundamental for assessing the region's attractiveness.

The mountainous regions of the Carpathians in Romania, Slovakia, and Poland have populations distributed across small rural communities, medium-sized towns, and a few large urban centers that serve as economic and tourist hubs. Although population density is low in the mountainous areas, these regions are inhabited by communities with traditions rooted in agriculture, animal husbandry, and tourism. Fig. 1 shows the largest cities in the Carpathian Mountains area. While Slovakia has more medium-sized settlements, and only Romania has large cities at the mountain periphery, none of the three countries stands out for urban development within the Carpathian region.

Fig. 1. Carpathian Mountains and main cities

Map: the authors

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHOD

For the analysis of the three mentioned indicators, we used data from OpenStreetMap (OSM), the most well-known Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) system (Goodchild, 2007), which emerged as a solution to the need for open and easily accessible geographic data.

All data from the OSM database can be downloaded for free in various spatial data formats. Additionally, there are a number of open-source tools available for processing this data and generating other formats (Mooney et al. 2013). The OSM project relies on experienced volunteers who dedicate their time to verifying, updating, and improving OSM data.

OSM provides data in structures called "ways" with attached attributes. Mountain trails, accommodation units, or ski slopes are examples of such structures with specific attributes (Fig. 2). This data is then converted into a database for more efficient management and to facilitate access to the required information.

OSM contains data about the entire Earth's surface and the objects on it, classified for almost any type of use. In our study, we focused on organizing and filtering data relevant to the analysis of tourism facilities. The indicators selected for this study are ski slopes, tourist trails, and accommodation units. Ski slopes were identified using the "piste:type" attribute from OSM, tourist trails are represented as "Relations – Hiking Route," and

accommodation units were extracted from the "accommodation" category in OSM. All this data was processed using a Geographic Information System (GIS).

Fig. 2. Example of OpenStreetMap data – ski slopes (a) and mountain trails (b).

Source: OpenStreetMap Contributors (2024). www.openstreetmap.org. Accessed 2 November 2024.

The data was imported using QGIS, an open-source tool, which enabled the efficient extraction and processing of data from OpenStreetMap. After importing the relevant data (ski slopes, mountain trails, and accommodation units), spatial analysis was conducted in ArcGIS Pro, a specialized software that provided an advanced set of tools for analyzing and visualizing geographic data. This spatial analysis method allowed for the identification and assessment of correlations between tourism facilities in mountain regions, and the generated maps were useful for highlighting their distribution based on various geographical and thematic criteria. The use of these GIS tools ensured precise data management and analysis capabilities, thus contributing to the creation of a detailed and well-founded study on tourism in the regions.

RESULTS

a. Accommodation Units

For the analysis of accommodation units in the Carpathian region, the data was extracted from the OpenStreetMap (OSM) database, including all common types of accommodation units: hotels, motels, hostels, guesthouses, and cabins. This data was filtered to include only the units located within the geographic boundaries of the Carpathian Mountains. This approach allowed for an accurate assessment of the distribution of tourism infrastructure in the mountain areas, excluding regions outside of this natural framework.

Fig. 3 illustrates the density of accommodation units in each of the three countries analyzed – Romania, Slovakia, and Poland – providing a clear comparative overview.

Fig. 3 Density of Accommodation Units

Data source: OpenStreetMap Contributors (2024). Map: authors

The analysis of the accommodation unit density in the Carpathians of Romania, Slovakia, and Poland highlights distinct tourism strategies. Poland, with a Carpathian area of 18,762 km², hosts 3,301 accommodation units, resulting in a density of 17.5 units per 100 km². This high density indicates a concentrated tourism infrastructure, focused on comfort and accessibility within a limited mountainous space.

Slovakia, with an area of 29,421 km² and 3,378 accommodation units, has a density of 11.4 units per 100 km². This intermediate value reflects a balanced approach, with developed infrastructure in a medium-sized mountainous area.

Romania, with the largest Carpathian region of 66,750 km² and 5,295 accommodation units, presents the lowest density, at just 7.9 units per 100 km². This figure suggests a more dispersed tourism strategy, with an emphasis on rural and eco-tourism, in line with the vastness of the region.

b. Mountain trails

To analyze the mountain trails, we extracted data related to Hiking Routes from OSM and divided them by the three studied countries. Fig. 4 presents the mountain trails in the studied Carpathian areas. Only the trails marked as tourist routes within the Carpathian Mountains were considered, with forest roads and unmarked paths excluded from the analysis.

Fig. 4. Mountain Trails in the Studied Area

Data source: OpenStreetMap Contributors (2024). Map: authors

For the analysis of mountain trails in the Carpathian regions, both the total length of the trails and their density relative to the mountainous area in each country were evaluated.

Slovakia has an extensive network of mountain trails, with a total of 41,928 km and an impressive density of 140 km/100 km², reflecting a well-developed infrastructure and high accessibility for hikers.

Poland has a total trail length of 18,967 km and a density of 101 km/100 km², highlighting a consistent coverage of the mountainous area.

Romania, although it has the largest mountainous area among the three countries, offers 29,846 km of mountain trails, with a density of only 44.71 km/100 km², suggesting a more dispersed network and less infrastructure development compared to Slovakia and Poland.

These differences reflect the countries' varied approaches to utilizing and promoting the tourism potential of the Carpathian Mountains.

c. Ski slopes

To analyze the skiing infrastructure, we extracted data from OSM related to downhill ski slopes (excluding the unmarked off-piste trails), which are generally located within larger ski resorts. As seen in Fig. 5, the ski slopes are clustered around the few major ski resorts in the three countries analyzed.

Fig. 4. Density of Ski Slopes in the Studied Area

Source of data: OpenStreetMap Contributors (2024). *Map:* authors

The Carpathian regions of Poland, Slovakia, and Romania show different densities of ski slopes, reflecting varied strategies for the development of mountain tourism.

Poland has the highest ski slope density, with 546.03 km of slopes, which represents 2.91 km/100 km², indicating a well-developed infrastructure focused on maximizing winter tourist activities.

Slovakia, with 672.56 km of slopes and a density of 2.29 km/100 km², reflects a balanced development of ski infrastructure adapted to the size of the mountain region.

Romania, with 327.44 km of slopes and a density of only 0.49 km/100 km², suggests a more limited infrastructure, consistent with a more dispersed mountain tourism strategy. These differences highlight the distinct priorities of each country in leveraging mountain tourism.

DISCUSSION

The integrated analysis of the density of accommodation units, mountain trails, and ski slopes in the Carpathian regions of Poland, Slovakia, and Romania reflects distinct tourism strategies influenced by economic, infrastructural, and geographical priorities. Poland, despite having the smallest Carpathian area, demonstrates an intensive and concentrated use of its territory, with the highest densities both in terms of accommodations (17.5 units/100 km²) and ski slopes (2.91 km/100 km²), followed by a

significant infrastructure of mountain trails (101 km/100 km²). This indicates a clear orientation towards intensive, accessible, and well-organized tourism.

Slovakia, with intermediate densities across all categories specific to winter sports (11.4 accommodation units/100 km², 2.29 km of ski slopes/100 km²), has the highest density of mountain trails at 140 km of trails/100 km². This reflects a balanced approach that combines the development of tourism infrastructure with environmental conservation and diversification of the tourist offering. It positions the country as a versatile destination, suitable for both winter sports and mountain hiking.

Romania, although it has the largest Carpathian area and the highest total number of accommodation units (5,295), has the lowest densities across all categories (7.9 accommodation units/100 km², 44.71 km of trails/100 km², and 0.49 km of ski slopes/100 km²). This suggests a more dispersed and less concentrated infrastructure, adapted to a tourism model focused on rural exploration and ecological tourism, rather than mass tourism.

These data highlight the differences in national strategies for capitalizing on the Carpathian Mountains, reflecting how each country balances accessibility, diverse tourism experiences, and the sustainable development of the region.

CONCLUSION

In this research, we analyzed the tourist potential of the mountainous regions of the Carpathians using data from OpenStreetMap (OSM), a free and open geographic information database. We investigated three main indicators : ski slopes, mountain trails, and accommodation units, to assess the distribution and accessibility of tourist facilities in the mountainous areas of Romania, Slovakia, and Poland. The analysis process was carried out with the help of GIS tools, namely QGIS and ArcGIS Pro, which allowed for the import, processing, and spatial analysis of OSM data. The results obtained demonstrated a correlation between the number of tourist facilities and areas with high potential for recreational activities and mountain tourism, confirming the importance of tourism infrastructure in attracting visitors to these regions.

By using OSM and GIS tools, we were able to identify the main tourist areas in the Carpathians, highlighting significant differences between the analyzed countries in terms of the distribution and availability of tourist facilities such as hiking trails, ski slopes, and accommodation units. The study showed that regions with more developed infrastructure, such as the Zakopane area in Poland, have a higher concentration of high-quality facilities, suggesting a greater attraction for tourists seeking premium services. Additionally, the analysis revealed that Slovakia is better prepared for summer tourism, with a significant number of hiking trails, but also sufficient facilities to support a considerable tourist flow during the winter season, especially on ski slopes. Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of planning and developing tourist infrastructure to support seasonal tourist flows in both summer and winter months, focusing on diversifying the tourist offer and enhancing the attractiveness of mountain regions.

Future research could explore the integration of additional data, such as climate or economic data, to obtain an even more detailed picture of the dynamics of mountain tourism. Additionally, analyzing the impact of tourism on the environment and local communities could provide an important layer of information for the development of

sustainable tourism in mountain regions. A potential direction for future research would be the use of data on the activities of companies operating in the tourism sector in the area or analyzing the evolution of tourist flows based on variations in temperature or snow cover.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization, M.D.; Methodology, A.D. and M.D.; Formal analysis, A.D.; Data verification, M.D.; Writing – original draft, M.D; Writing – review and editing, A.D. and M.D.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

USE OF AI IN THE SCIENTIFIC WRITING

During the preparation of this article, the authors used the ChatGPT tool to generate suggestions for phrasing parts of the text and to optimize the clarity of expressions. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content according to academic requirements and take full responsibility for the content of the publication

DATA AVAILABILITY

The derived data supporting the conclusions of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

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